

LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

Recommended citation of this article

Young-Scholten, M., Peyton, J. K., Sosinski, M., & Cabeza, A. M. (2015). LESLLA Teachers' Views of the Knowledge and Skills They Need: An International Study. *LESLLA Symposium Proceedings*, 10(1), 165–185. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8024410>

Citation for LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

This article is part of a collection of articles based on presentations from the 2014 Symposium held at Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands. Please note that the year of publication is often different than the year the symposium was held. We recommend the following citation when referencing the edited collection.

Van de Craats, I., Kurvers, J., & van Hout, R. (Eds.) (2015). *Adult literacy, second language and cognition*. Centre for Language Studies. Centre for Language Studies. <https://lesllasp.journals.publicknowledgeproject.org/index.php/lesllasp/issue/view/474>

About the Organization

LESLLA aims to support adults who are learning to read and write for the first time in their lives in a new language. We promote, on a worldwide, multidisciplinary basis, the sharing of research findings, effective pedagogical practices, and information on policy.

LESLLA Symposium Proceedings

<https://lesllasp.journals.publicknowledgeproject.org>

Website

<https://www.leslla.org/>

LESLLA TEACHERS' VIEWS OF THE KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS THEY NEED: AN INTERNATIONAL STUDY

Martha Young-Scholten, Newcastle University

Joy Kreeft Peyton, Center for Applied Linguistics, Washington, DC

Marcin Sosinski and Antonio Manjón Cabeza, University of Granada

Abstract

It is recognized that skilled and knowledgeable teachers are key to facilitating student learning and promoting their success. However, those who teach adult immigrants who have limited education and literacy in their native/home language and are learning the language of their new country as a second or additional language (LESLLA learners) typically have limited to no specific training or professional development that prepares them to work with this population. This article reports on the work of the EU-SPEAK 2 project, which conducted two surveys of teachers and program managers in European countries and North America, to determine the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that they believe they have and that they need. Results show that practitioners focus primarily on *skills* they need to teach effectively rather than on research and knowledge that undergird and support those skills. Skills that they indicated they need include: the ability to use specific teaching methods, conversational situations, materials, and instructional approaches to teach oral language skills and to guide learners in the process of developing reading and writing strategies that they can use independently in their daily lives. Desire for better understanding of the principles and the processes that underlie approaches/skills received lower scores.

Keywords: LESLLA learners; teacher knowledge, skills, and attitudes; teacher training and professional development needs; online study circle; curriculum framework

1. Introduction

It has long been recognized that skilled and knowledgeable teachers are key in supporting each student in a classroom so that all students can reach their full potential (Guskey 2000). It has also been understood that specific knowledge

Ineke van de Craats, Jeanne Kurvers and Roeland van Hout (eds.)

Adult literacy, second language and cognition

Nijmegen: CLS, 2015, pp. 165-185

and skills are required for teaching in primary/elementary school and secondary school and for teaching specific student populations (e.g., gifted students; students with disabilities; deaf and hard of hearing students). This understanding has translated into specific qualifications required for teachers in primary and secondary school programs and, more recently in some countries, college and university programs. However, in the education of adult immigrants who have limited education and literacy in their home language and native country and who are learning the language of their new country as a second or additional language, no such understandings currently exist about specific knowledge and skills needed for teachers to support students in reaching their potential. In most countries, no specific teaching qualifications are required for teachers working with this population of learners (henceforth referred to as “low-educated second language and literacy acquisition by adults, LESLLA”), and little specific teacher training or professional development exists.

By definition, LESLLA learners have received too little education to possess literacy in their first or home language or in any other language. Lack of literacy means that in this arena, these learners are similar to pre-school children, and teachers with primary school teacher training and experience can use at least some of the knowledge and skills they have to teach LESLLA learners. This position is justified by findings from studies revealing important commonalities between adults and children, which indicate that there is no critical period for learning to read (Kurvers & Van de Craats 2008; Pettitt & Tarone 2015; Young-Scholten & Strom 2006). At the same time, LESLLA learners’ minimal linguistic competence in their second language (L2) means that they are similar to other adult L2 learners, and teachers with secondary or college/university teaching experience can use some of their knowledge and skills to teach them. That they can only use *some* of their knowledge and skills indicates a gap. This is a crucial gap. The strong need for specific training and professional development for these teachers is underscored on the one hand by the persistent failure of LESLLA learners observed in education programs around the world to move beyond basic language and literacy in their L2 (e.g., from below level A1 to level B1 of the six-level Common European Framework of Reference/CEFR for languages (Council of Europe 2001; Kurvers & Van de Craats 2008)). This need is underscored on the other hand by LESLLA learners’ accelerated progress when they are taught by qualified teachers (Condelli, Cronen, Bos, Tseng, & Altuna 2010). These trends point to the need for teachers with knowledge and skills specific to teaching adult LESLLA learners.

Primary school training and experience is insufficient, because LESLLA adults learning to read are not like children learning to read for the first time. They are learning to read for the first time in a language that they are also just

starting to learn to speak. Primary school teaching qualifications provide a start toward the knowledge and skills needed, but these qualifications are not sufficient. Likewise, LESLLA learners are not like secondary school or college/university students, and qualifications for teaching and experience in teaching in these contexts are also not sufficient. While LESLLA teachers can certainly benefit if they have knowledge and skills of primary, secondary, and college/university teachers, they need additional knowledge and skills. As a starting point, because LESLLA learners are adults and immigrants, their learning trajectories are subject to variation due to a number of additional factors, most of which do not apply to children or to educated second language learners. Such factors considerably expand the knowledge and skills needed by LESLLA teachers.

Since 2005, LESLLA symposia and proceedings have revealed the many ways in which low-educated adult immigrants develop basic literacy and the creative ways that teachers support them in the face of fluctuating national policies and funding for adult basic skills provision. Training and continued professional development of LESLLA teachers is often fragmented, even when it does exist, and most teachers lack specific teaching qualifications. In some countries, reliance on volunteers in adult education programs can mean that teachers may not even have primary, secondary, or college/university teaching qualifications (see, e.g., Young-Scholten 2012).

The number of non-literate adults around the world is decreasing somewhat (from 862 million illiterate adults, mostly women, in 2000, which is considered a hugely undercounted number) to an estimated 780 million in 2012, according to the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2014a, b). There are and will continue to be adults who immigrate to post-industrialized countries without being literate. They face dependency on benefits if they cannot develop language and literacy skills beyond basic levels (e.g., Bynner 2001; CEFR Basic User levels A1/A2 of the European Union, Council of Europe 2001; Dustmann & Fabbri 2003). However, before providing recommendations concerning what such specialized training and development should involve, we need consensus on the knowledge and skills that LESLLA-specific teacher qualifications require. We also need to know whether and how teachers are developing these teaching skills, on their own or with professional development and support. In this paper, we report on measures taken to address these two areas. The information gained will provide guidance for developing a curriculum framework for LESLLA teacher training and professional development. The goal is to equip teachers of low-educated adult immigrants with the same high levels of specialized knowledge and skills that primary, secondary, and college/university teachers have. Since immigration of low-educated immigrant adults is supranational, the curriculum

will also be supranational and will take into account local variations in language, orthography, and culture.

2. Methodology

In January 2014, the EU-Speak-2 project, which includes four phases of activity, began work on the Phases 1 and 2. These were completed in August 2014, and are discussed in this article. Phase 3 involves piloting an online professional development module that addresses some of the needs indicated in the survey, and Phase 4 involves developing the outline of an international LESLLA teacher training and development curriculum framework. The project is carried out by European partners at the Universities of Amsterdam; Cologne; Granada; Jyväskylä in Finland; and Newcastle and three U.S. partners: American Institutes for Research and Center for Applied Linguistics (both Washington, DC), and Virginia Commonwealth University (Richmond, Virginia). Phase 1 surveyed the knowledge and skills that teachers of LESLLA learners and managers of programs that serve them believe they have, need, and want to gain in professional development. The survey, which included a combination of multiple choice and open-ended questions, was sent via email using Survey Monkey, and respondents wrote their answers. When this survey was completed, we used the results to compile a comprehensive list of knowledge and skills specific to LESLLA teaching and asked experts in LESLLA education to respond to this list. These respondents were program managers, teacher trainers, activists, and researchers in the same countries as those of the survey respondents as well as countries bordering them. Phase 2 then surveyed teachers, using the same format, about their opportunities to develop LESLLA-relevant knowledge and skills.

One of the recurring themes in the survey responses has been the need to provide materials and information to teachers in their native languages. EU-Speak project partners were regularly reminded that use of English as a professional lingua franca is not always appropriate for LESLLA professionals who are teaching the language and literacy of the country they work in. This has had implications for translation of the survey questions and has ongoing implications for the ways that the online professional development modules (Phases 3 and 4) are delivered and the curriculum is framed.

In the following section, we describe the design and outcomes of each survey.

3. Survey of knowledge and skills of teachers and managers

3.1. Methodology

The starting point for development of the first survey was to review the set of knowledge and skills outlined by the Nordic Adult Literacy Network (Franker & Christensen, 2013), which lists specific competencies required of professional teachers who are teaching initial and functional literacy to adults whose mother tongue is not a Nordic language. The next step was grouping those and other knowledge and skills into five major categories and then producing various drafts until a final set of 30 items was agreed on by the project partners. To get a sense of whether teachers and managers understood the need for these knowledge and skills in the work they were doing, we asked for each question: (1) *Is this important in your work with low-educated adult immigrants?* Respondents used a four-point Likert scale with the descriptors: *Not at all important; Somewhat important; Important; Very important*. To get a sense of whether they wished to gain these knowledge and skills, we asked: (2) *Is this important for your professional development?* Using the same four-point scale, the responses could be: *No, I don't need to learn more about this topic; Yes, I am somewhat interested; I am interested in learning more; I am very interested and eager to learn more*. Respondents were also asked about their position (manager, teacher, manager and teacher) and work status (full-time, part-time, paid, volunteer), their level of education and fields of study, their years of experience working with LESLLA and other learners, their training and professional development for working with adults, and the levels of literacy of the adults they work with. The surveys were then translated into Dutch, Finnish, German, and Spanish and uploaded to an open source survey application, LimeSurvey, which was hosted by the project's Spanish partner, the University of Granada. Potential respondents were made aware of the survey via user lists and networks in each partner's country and in several additional countries (see below). Respondents were LESLLA teachers or program managers. The survey is available at this link: <http://research.ncl.ac.uk/eu-speak/surveysandresults/>

3.2. Results

Respondents

We aimed for 300 responses (50 from each partner country) and received 308 completed surveys, from the partner countries and beyond. Because most potential respondents were made aware of the questionnaire via user lists, we do not have statistics on how many individuals were contacted initially. An

additional 48 individuals began the survey but did not complete it for various reasons, including concluding that the questions were not relevant to them. (We realized during our analysis that our initial questions could have given this impression.)

As can be seen in Table 1, the highest response rates were from Finland, the United States, and Spain. The lower response rates were from the Netherlands, Belgium, and Ireland. It is possible that the lower response rate in the Netherlands and Belgium was because the survey was in English. It is also possible that the lists used limited the number of teachers reached. Future surveys will be available in the languages of the countries involved, and we will make more effort to disseminate the survey through colleagues in the field.

Table 1: *Survey responses by country*

Country	Number	Percent of total
Finland	66	21.4%
United States	59	19.2%
Spain	56	18.2%
United Kingdom	49	15.9%
Canada	25	8.1%
Netherlands + Belgium	19	6.2%
Ireland	12	3.9%
Other (Afghanistan, Australia, China, Germany, Italy, New Zealand, Thailand)	22	7.1%
Total	308	100%

In response to the options provided on the survey, most of the respondents self-identified as teachers (218) or teacher/managers (56). Very few identified as being only managers (14).

Most respondents reported working in full-time positions (242), of which roughly half were paid (115) and half voluntary (127), with more full-time voluntary than paid teachers.

About one-third had been teaching adult learners for one year or less (104), one-third between one and five years (99), and one-third for more than five years (105). Most reported working with adults with limited education and literacy. Respondents reported having more experience teaching adults oral skills than literacy.

Most of the training that respondents had received for working with adult learners focused on adult language acquisition rather than on adult literacy.

Responses regarding knowledge and skills needed

The first step in analyzing the data was to assign values to the responses to each of the following questions, where the lowest score was 0 and the highest score was 3: *Is this important in your work with low-educated adult immigrants?* and *(2) Is this important for your professional development?*

Responses by country

Response scores from all of the countries, to both questions, were high, at least 2 (or close to 2) out of 3, pointing to a high level of interest in and need for gaining the knowledge and skills mentioned in the questionnaire items. Although the differences in responses by country were not statistically significant in most cases, responses from Australia and Spain indicate a higher desire for additional professional development than those from the other countries. There are probably good reasons for this. In both countries the focus on immigrants learning the language of the country (English and Spanish respectively) is relatively new. In Spain, most of the focus in adult education is on oral language learning and not on literacy, and on primary and secondary school language learners and not on basic skills for adult immigrants learning Spanish. In the United Kingdom, United States, and Netherlands/Flemish-speaking Belgium, respondents show a lower need to learn more than those in the other countries. It is possible that more professional development is available for teachers of adults in these countries, with a focus on both oral language and literacy. However, as noted above, most of the differences from country to country were not statistically significant.

Responses by type of position held

Most of the teachers and managers responded that the knowledge and skills listed in the survey were *Very Important* or *Important*. Teachers and teacher/managers expressed a higher need for knowledge and skills than those who were just managers. This makes sense, since the items in the survey focus on classroom instruction rather than on program type and program structure.

Responses by work level and status

Full-time, paid respondents showed a greater need/desire for learning than part-time paid or volunteer respondents. This is expected, since the former have the time and resources to devote to professional development work.

Responses by amount of experience teaching LESLLA learners

Those with one to one-and-a-half years of experience teaching adult learners (but not specifically LESLLA learners; see below) indicated a higher need for

gaining more knowledge and skills than those with no experience. It is possible that those with some teaching experience have a greater understanding of their need to learn more than those with no experience. Not surprisingly, those with over 20 years of experience indicated the lowest levels of need.

Responses by type of professional development desired

Respondents indicated a greater interest in receiving professional development on adult language acquisition/oral skills than on adult literacy, but the differences in interest between these areas were statistically not significant.

Responses regarding knowledge and skills needed

The appendix shows the scores in response to the items in the survey, listed from the highest to the lowest. In both areas – knowledge and skills considered important in teaching and desire to learn more – it is clear that practitioners are focusing primarily on *skills* they need to teach effectively.

Many more items with high responses focused on skills than on knowledge. These include the following skills. The ability to ...

- Use teaching methods that facilitate learners' active participation in class and contribute their knowledge and experience
- Use authentic conversational situations and materials in teaching that reflect learners' daily experiences and meet their needs
- Develop and use materials that learners have encountered in their daily lives
- Guide learners in the process of developing reading and writing strategies that they can use independently in their daily lives
- Use instructional approaches to teach oral language skills.

Areas of *knowledge* that received the highest scores are closely related to these skills. Understanding and awareness of ...

- Learners' backgrounds, current situations, and learning potentials to guide course planning and teaching
- Current teaching materials suitable for developing language and literacy skills
- The effect of learners' first language(s) when learning the second/additional language
- The kinds of written information that learners encounter in their daily lives.

Generally, desire for better understanding and awareness of the principles and the processes (knowledge) that underlie teaching approaches and skills received lower scores.

4. Consultation with experts

Following the analysis of the survey results, an email message was sent to experts in each partner country. The email gave a brief summary of the major findings, with the top 10 and bottom 10 scores in each partner language and a link to the report produced on the survey. They were asked the following four questions: (1) Do you agree that these 10 items are very important? (2) Do you have any comments to add about this outcome? (3) Do you agree that the bottom 10 items are less important than the top 10 items? (4) Do you have any comments to add about this outcome? The results of this consultation were fed into a final set of knowledge and skills, to which was added another category: Attitudes/Dispositions. (See the final list of knowledge, skills, and attitudes at this link: <http://research.ncl.ac.uk/eu-speak/surveysandresults/>)

5. Survey of teachers' opportunities to gain LESLLA-relevant knowledge and skills

5.1. Methodology

A second survey was sent to a smaller group of selected LESLLA practitioners to ask about the pre-service training and in-service professional development available to them and what opportunities they had taken advantage of (available at this link: <http://research.ncl.ac.uk/eu-speak/surveysandresults/>)

Again the platform used was LimeSurvey, hosted by the University of Granada. Potential respondents were made aware of the survey via user lists and networks. Respondents were not necessarily the same individuals who responded to the first survey, since respondents to the first survey were anonymous, and we had no way to contact or track them. We assumed that many would be the same individuals, and that the two groups of respondents would be sufficiently similar. The results support this.

5.2. Results

We expected fewer responses to the second survey than to the first one, given our level of outreach each time. There were 137 respondents to Survey 2. Table 2 shows the number and percent of respondents by language and country. There were also six responses (listed in the category Other) from Afghanistan, China, Ireland, Italy, New Zealand, and Thailand. This survey was available in the languages of the partner countries in the project.

Table 2: Responses by language and country

Language	Number	Percent of total
English	45	33%
- from Australia (6-4%)		
- from Canada (8-6%)		
- from United Kingdom (22-16%)		
- from United States (9-7%)		
Spanish	26	19%
Dutch	29	22%
- from Belgium (20-15%)		
- from the Netherlands (9-7%)		
Finnish (Finland)	19	13%
German (Germany)	12	9%
Other	6	4%
Total	137	100%

Age

We did not ask the age of respondents in Survey 1, but we decided to do so in Survey 2, adding it as an optional response item. 128 out of 137 responded to this question, and their mean age was 46, with respondents in the following age categories.

Table 3: Respondents by age

Age range	< 35 years	35-45 years	45-55 years	> 55 years	Total
Number of participants	33	34	31	30	128

Gender

Unlike in Survey 1, we asked about gender in Survey 2. Again, this was an optional question, and 124 responded. The overwhelming majority of respondents was female (116), and a small minority was male (18).

Type of position held and work status

In response to the items provided in Survey 2, respondents self-identified as teacher, trainer, or manager. The majority self-identified as teacher (120) with combinations including trainer and manager. The majority held paid positions, either full time (55) or part time (62) with a much smaller number holding volunteer positions, either full time (1) or part time (19).

Experience teaching adult learners

In Survey 2, we fine-tuned the question about teaching experience, this time asking how many years' experience respondents had teaching literate adult immigrants and how many years' experience they had teaching adult immigrants with limited or no literacy. At least half of the respondents had more than five years' experience teaching adult immigrants with limited or no literacy.

Table 4: Respondents' experience teaching adult learners

Experience teaching	Years of experience			Total
	< 1 year	1-5 years	> 5 years	
Literate immigrants	20	41	76	137
Immigrants with limited or no literacy	36	34	67	137

Training received for working with adult learners

The training that respondents have received focused on working with adult learners is limited: a mean of ten hours in the past year and 44 hours in the past five years, including the past year. Respondents from Germany and Spain have received significantly more training in the past year than those from other countries.

Learners' levels of education

The levels of education of the learners that respondents work with was reported as low. It is interesting to note that 24% of the respondents reported that they do not know the level of education of the learners they work with.

- More than two years, but not full primary education: 77% of respondents
- No education: 62%
- Don't know learners' level of education: 24%

Focus of teaching

In response to the multiple choice question about the focus of their teaching, most respondents reported that they teach oral communication skills, writing, vocabulary, and reading (over 85% in each case) with many fewer reporting that they teach practical life skills (health literacy, employment, citizenship, and safety; 55% or lower for each of these; see Table 5).

Training to prepare for teaching

In response to the multiple choice question about the focus of the training they have received, respondents reported receiving much less training in each area than their focus in teaching. For example, while 95% reported that they teach oral communication skills, only 47% reported receiving training in oral language development. While 62% reported teaching grammar, only 28% reported receiving training in language structure. While 55% reported teaching health literacy, only 8% reported receiving training in that area. The differences between these two areas are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: *Content taught in class and focus of training received by respondents (N=137)*

Content taught in class	Respondents (N)	%	Training focus	Respondents (N)	%
Oral communication skills	113	95%	Teaching methodology	99	72%
Writing	108	91%	Materials	76	56%
Vocabulary	108	91%	Oral language development	65	47%
Reading	107	90%	Instructional strategies	63	46%
Listening	103	87%	Lesson planning	62	45%
Culture	86	72%	Assessment	61	45%
Life skills	82	69%	Teaching in mixed-ability classes	53	39%
Grammar	74	62%	Language structure	38	28%
Health literacy	65	55%	Life skills	31	23%
Employment	62	52%	Employment	18	13%
Citizenship/Visa	40	34%	Safety	14	10%
Safety	35	29%	Health literacy	11	8%
Other	14	12%	Numeracy	9	7%
			Other	14	10%

Responses regarding knowledge and skills needed by practitioners

In this survey, we asked not only about knowledge and skills needed by practitioners but also about attitudes needed to be effective with LESLLA learners (e.g., the teacher approaches teaching from the perspective of the learners, has high expectations for the learners, and works with other teachers to continue learning). We also added a section asking about Numeracy. Responses are listed at this link: <http://research.ncl.ac.uk/eu-speak/surveysandresults/>

Responses were similar to those in the first survey, with a focus on the need for specific instructional approaches and understandings and less focus on the need to understand research that underlies specific approaches.

6. Conclusion and next steps

The survey results show that all of the statements about the knowledge and skills that teachers need for working effectively with LESLLA learners received relatively high scores. Both teachers and managers want to gain the knowledge and skills mentioned in the survey items. Responses also show that respondents have had more training on teaching language acquisition and oral language skills than on adult literacy. While respondents indicated their need for specific skills for working with these learners, they seem to be less aware of the background knowledge that underpins the ability to develop and use these skills.

Results from the two surveys have guided our development of a pilot online study circle for teachers who work with LESLLA learners in countries around the world. The outcomes of the study circle will inform and guide development of an international curriculum framework.

In developing these professional development opportunities, we are focusing on instructional approaches and materials underpinned by research and theory that teachers and managers without specific LESLLA training can use immediately. The opportunities impart information to LESLLA professionals about the diverse factors that can affect LESLLA learners' trajectories in their development of oral and literacy skills (e.g., to CEFR B1 level and beyond). This approach to an international curriculum aligns with the interests and needs that respondents to the surveys and the expert consultation indicated. The respondents on whom these conclusions are based come from countries in which there are LESLLA learners. There is still a need to conduct a survey that reaches a wider spread of countries, including those in which adults who are not immigrants to the country are learning to read in the official language of the country (e.g., English) for the first time as adults.

Disclaimer

EU-Speak 2 project reference EACEA 539478-LLP-1-UK-GRUNDTVIG-GMP has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication (communication) reflects only the views of the author(s), and the Commission

cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to EU-SPEAK project partners who helped to develop and disseminate the survey and analyze the results: Paula Bosch, Larry Condelli, Nancy Faux, Sneah Khanna, Maisa Martin, Yvonne Ritchie, Andreas Rohde, and Taina Tammelin-Laine. We are also grateful to Jerónimo Cabeza, Pilar López, and Carmen Sánchez, from the University of Granada, Spain, who participated in analysis of the LimeSurvey data.

References

- Bynner, J. (2001). *Outline of the research, exploratory analysis, and summary of the main results*. London, England: Centre for Longitudinal Studies, Institute of Education.
- Condelli, L., Cronen, S., Bos, J., Tseng, F., & Altuna, J. (2010). *The impact of a literacy intervention for low-educated adult ESL learners*. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education, NCEE, Institute of Education Sciences.
- Council of Europe. (2001). *Common European framework of reference for languages: Learning, teaching, and assessment*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. http://www.coe.int/t/Dg4/Linguistic/Source/Framework_EN.pdf
- Dustman, C., & Fabbri, F. (2003). Language proficiency and labour market performance of immigrants in the UK, *Economic Journal*, 113, 695–717.
- Franker, Q., & Christensen, L. (2013). Description of teachers' competence in initial and functional literacy for adults with non-Nordic mother tongues. *Alfarådet, The Nordic Adult Literacy Network*. www.alfaradet.net
- Guskey, T. R. (2000). *Evaluating professional development*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Kurvers, J., & Van de Craats, I. (2008). What makes the illiterate language learning genius? In M. Young-Scholten (ed.), *Low-educated second language and literacy acquisition* (pp. 49-62). Durham: Roundtuit.
- Pettitt, N., & Tarone, E. (2015). Following Roba: What happens when a low-educated adult immigrant learns to read. *Writing Systems Research*. Advance online publication. doi: 10.1080/17586801.2014.987199
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2014a). *International literacy data 2014*. <http://www.uis.unesco.org/literacy/Pages/literacy-data-release-2014.aspx>

- UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2014b). *The United Nations literacy decade (2003-2012)*. (2014). France: Author.
<http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0013/001354/135400e.pdf>
- Young-Scholten, M. (2012, August 30). *The EU-Speak Project: Finding and sharing European treasure*. Keynote address presented at the annual LESLLA symposium, Jyväskylä, Finland. <http://eu-speak.org/blog/finding-and-sharing-european-treasure#attachments>
- Young-Scholten, M., & Strom, N. (2006). First-time L2 readers: Is there a critical period? In I. van de Craats, J. Kurvers, & M. Young-Scholten (eds.), *Low educated adult second language and literacy acquisition. Proceedings of the inaugural conference* (pp. 45-68). Utrecht: LOT.

Project Web Pages

EU-SPEAK 2 project: www.eu-speak.com

Surveys 1 and 2:

<http://research.ncl.ac.uk/eu-speak/projectreports/eu-speak2internationalsurveys/>

Responses to Survey 2:

<http://research.ncl.ac.uk/media/sites/researchwebsites/eu-speak2/EU-SPEAK%20%20Knowledge,%20Skills,%20Understanding,%20Attitudes.pdf>

Appendix. Knowledge and skills survey 1: Item ratings*Is this important in your work with low-educated adult immigrants?*

Skills		Knowledge	
Ability to ...	Score	Understanding/awareness of/familiarity with...	Score
Use teaching methods that facilitate learners' active participation in a classroom environment and that allow them to contribute their own knowledge and experience	2.85		
Use authentic conversational situations in teaching that reflect learners' daily experiences	2.77		
Develop and use materials during the course that low-educated immigrant adults encounter in their daily lives	2.74		
		Learners' backgrounds, current situations, and learning potentials when planning and teaching your course	2.69
Guide learners in the process of developing reading and writing strategies that can apply independently outside the classroom and in situations involving written language	2.66	Current teaching materials suitable for developing low-educated adult immigrants' oral language and literacy skills	2.66
Use methods to teach oral language skills --pronunciation, grammar, pragmatics, and vocabulary -- in a second language to non-literate immigrant adults	2.62		
		That learners' competence and skills in their mother-tongue/first language affect literacy development in the second language	2.56
		Kinds of written information that learners encounter and use in their daily lives	2.55

Use a variety of multimodal materials for teaching reading and writing and modify them to meet learners' needs in their daily lives and work-related situations	2.53		
Analyze different materials currently available for low-educated adult immigrants to make sure that they are engaging and appropriate for their reading levels	2.51	Potential challenges to learning of psychological and physical conditions	2.51
		Stages of vocabulary learning and instructional methods for facilitating word learning	2.43
		Significance of phonological awareness in literacy training and its application in teaching	2.36
		Complexity of literacy skills	2.36
		Current information about learners' social, cultural, educational, and language backgrounds	2.33
		Ways to chart and analyze learners' progress in literacy	2.88
		Ways to chart and analyze learners' progress in oral language proficiency	2.27
		Information technology, digital tools, and media, including social media; how learners use them; and how they can be used to support teaching and learning	2.27
		Relationship between oral language mastery and methods for teaching reading and writing skills	2.26
		That learners' competence in their mother-tongue/first language affects second language acquisition	2.26
		Principles and processes of adult learning	2.25

	Language acquisition in different contexts and by different types of learners	2.25
	Spoken language as a system, including phonology, grammar, pragmatics, and vocabulary	2.22
	Stages of grammar learning and instructional methods for facilitating grammar learning	2.18
	How conditions governing spoken language and its acquisition relate to teaching low-educated immigrant adults	2.11
	Similarities and differences between spoken and written language in monolingual contexts	2.11
	Similarities and differences in uses of spoken and written language in multilingual and multicultural contexts	2.06
Base instruction that facilitates reading and writing development of second language learners on sound theories and research	1.95	
	Literacy skills from an historic, political, sociocultural, and linguistic perspective	1.72

Is this important for your professional development?

Skills	Knowledge	Score
Ability to ...	Understanding/awareness of/familiarity with ...	
	Current teaching materials suitable for developing low-educated adult immigrants' oral language and literacy skills	2.41
Use teaching methods that facilitate learners' active participation in a classroom environment and that allow them to contribute their own knowledge and experience		2.38
Guide learners in the process of developing reading and writing strategies that they can apply independently outside the classroom and in situations involving written language		2.37
Develop and use materials during the course that low-educated immigrant adults encounter in their daily lives		2.27
Use methods to teach oral language skills --pronunciation, grammar, pragmatics, and vocabulary -- in a second language to non-literate immigrant adults	Learners' backgrounds, current situations, and learning potentials when planning and teaching your course	2.26
	Complexity of literacy skills	2.22
Use a variety of multimodal materials for teaching reading and writing and modify them to meet learners' needs in their daily lives and work-related situations		2.19
Use authentic conversational situations in teaching that reflects learners' daily experiences		2.17
	Potential challenges to learning of psychological and physical conditions	2.16

	Information technology, digital tools, and media, including social media; how learners use them; and how they can be used to support teaching and learning	2.13
	Ways to chart and analyze learners' progress in literacy	2.13
	That learners' competence and skills in their mother-tongue/first language affect literacy development in the second language	2.11
	Stages of vocabulary learning and instructional methods for facilitating word learning	2.11
	Significance of phonological awareness in literacy training and its application in teaching	2.08
Analyze different materials currently available for low-educated adult immigrants to make sure that they are engaging and appropriate for their reading levels	2.07	
	Language acquisition in different contexts and by different types of learners	2.04
	Relationship between oral language mastery and methods for teaching reading and writing skills	2.03
	Ways to chart and analyze learners' progress in oral language proficiency	2.01
	Current information about learners' social, cultural, educational, and language backgrounds	1.95
	Similarities and differences in uses of spoken and written language in multilingual and multicultural contexts	1.92
	How conditions governing spoken language and its	1.91

		acquisition relate to teaching low-educated immigrant adults	
		Kinds of written information that learners encounter and use in their daily lives	1.90
Base instruction that facilitates reading and writing development of second language learners on sound theories and research	1.90	Stages of grammar learning and instructional methods for facilitating grammar learning	1.90
		Spoken language as a system, including phonology, grammar, pragmatics, and vocabulary	1.88
		Literacy skills from an historic, political, sociocultural and linguistic perspective	1.84
		Similarities and differences between spoken and written language in monolingual contexts	1.83
		That learners' competence in their mother-tongue/first language affects second language acquisition	1.82
		Principles and processes of adult learning	1.82